

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART II.

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In the acenaphthenequinone series Martinet's rule (*Rev. Gen. Mat. Col.*, 1921, 25, 17) is applicable to 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Bezdik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, 29, 386; E.P. 344/08; G. P. 226244; Mayer and Schönfelder, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2972; G. P. 213504; E. P. 20003/08; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423) and in the isatin series to 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigos (Bezdik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, 29, 376; E. P. 17162/06; G. P. 241327; E. P. 19158/07; G. P. 277358) as far as one Me group in the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule is concerned (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 679; 1936, 13, 94; Guha and Basu-Mallik, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 395; Guha, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 240). The dyestuffs obtained by the condensation of α -chloride of isatin and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene and 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene respectively and their derivatives may also be compared. (F. P. 693903 of 14/4/1930; *Chem Zentr.*, 1931, 102, I, 2944; A.P. 1850758 of 10/12/1930. *Chem. Zentr.*, 1932, 103, II, 1374).

In another communication (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 659) 5-methyl derivatives of benzylidene-2-thionaphthene (Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 543) and its various substituted products and also that of bis-2-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo (Friedlander and Risse, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1924) were studied. The object of this investigation was to obtain their corresponding 6-methyl derivatives and to examine if Martinet's rule holds good in the series as well having only one Me group in the thionaphthene part of the molecule of the compounds.

With this object in view, 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Friedlander, 9, 589; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2293) was condensed with glyoxal, benzaldehyde, *p*-nitro-, and *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde respectively and the corresponding dyestuffs obtained. Here those aldehydes only have been selected which gave rise to compounds of fairly prominent colours in the 5-methyl series (Guha, *loc. cit.*). The 6-methyl compounds described here resemble the corresponding 5-methyl derivatives in crystallising power, in solubility and in developing shades on wool and on cotton, unless mentioned otherwise in the experimental part. The colours, developed on wool and on cotton from the substances described in this part, are pronouncedly lighter in shade than those obtained from the corresponding 5-methyl compounds (Guha, *loc. cit.*) showing that Martinet's rule is

also applicable to this series of compounds. A comparison of some of the colours on wool and on cotton obtained from the compounds of the two series is given below.

Names.	Dyeing shades	
	on wool.	on cotton.
bis-2(6 Methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo	Scarlet red	Deep scarlet-red
bis-2(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo	Dark red	Violet-red
4'-Nitro-benzylidene-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene	Deep yellow	Yellowish orange
4'-Nitro-benzylidene-2-(5 methyl)-thionaphthene	Orange yellow	Light orange
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene	Cinnabar red	Light pink
4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2(5-methyl)-thionaphthene	Cinnabar red	Pink

2:3-Naphthoxythiophene (Friedlander and Woroshzow, *Annalen*, 1912, 388, 18) was condensed with acenaphthenequinone and a blue-red dye was obtained. This dye on bromination gave a blue-red product (Schwz P. P. 107133-35 of 29/3/23. *Chem. Zentr.*, 1925, 96, II, 860). Later on Dutt (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 1326. *cf.* E. P. 209092 of 27/12/23) prepared the same mother compound and has described it to be rose-violet. The present author has condensed 3-chloro-, 3-bromo-, and β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone with 2:3-naphthoxythiophene respectively with a view to study the effect of different elements or groups on the colour of the mother compound and the corresponding dyes prepared. These are all red-violet substances, the methoxy derivative possessing the deepest shade of the three. They are sparingly soluble in acetic acid, amyl alcohol, and less so in alcohol, and are soluble in nitrobenzene. They melt when heated above 305° and quickly volatilise evolving vapours of the respective substances. They dissolve in strong sulphuric acid with a green colour from which water reprecipitates the original substances. The halogenated products are reduced by alkaline hydrosulphite producing green vat from which the original dyes are reprecipitated by oxidation with air. The methoxy derivative could not be easily converted into a soluble vat. The dirty white colour developed, after repeated trial, on cotton from the alkaline vat turned light violet by atmospheric oxidation. [*cf.* 2-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthylene-indigo, its 5-methyl and 6-methyl derivatives only. Staudinger-Goldstein and Schlenker, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 342; Guha, *loc. cit.*].

EXPERIMENTAL.

The *bis-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo* and *benzylidene-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene* described below were prepared in the same way as the corresponding 5-methyl compounds (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

bis-2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-ethyleneindigo.

It was prepared from glyoxal sodium bisulphite (0.568 g.) in 15 c.c. of water and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). The dye (0.381 g.) crystallised from toluene in deep red shining needles, m.p. 300° (decomp.). It is soluble in chloroform, difficultly in benzene, toluene, and sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride and less so in petroleum ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour and dyes wool in pleasant scarlet red shades from an acid bath and cotton in deep scarlet red shades from a deep yellow vat. (Found : S, 18.71. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S, 18.28 per cent).

Benzylidene-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene.

It was obtained as yellow rectangular substance from benzaldehyde (0.424 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.). The product (0.839 g.) crystallised from dilute alcohol in silky long yellow rectangular crystals, m. p. 134-35°. It dyes wool in yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: S, 12.46. $C_{18}H_{12}OS$ requires S, 12.69 per cent).

4'-Nitro-benzylidene-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene separated as yellowish-orange crystalline precipitate from *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.453 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 22 c.c. of hot absolute alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3 c.c.) The substance (0.738 g.) crystallised in long silky yellowish orange needles, m. p. 228-29°. It is moderately soluble in alcohol. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is purple. It dyes wool in deep yellow shades from acid bath and cotton in yellowish

orange shades from an orange vat. (Found : S, 11'19. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3NS$ requires S, 10'77 per cent).

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene.—A greenish yellow crystalline precipitate of the hydrochloride of the base was obtained by condensing *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0'596 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0'656 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (13 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1'5 c.c.) It gave on washing with dilute alcohol the red dye (0'985 g.). It crystallised from methyl alcohol in hexagonal iridescent prisms, m.p. 193°. It is soluble in petroleum ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet red colouration. It dyes wool in cinnabar red shades and cloth in light pink colour from a faintly red vat. (Found : S, 11'13. $C_{18}H_{17}ONS$ requires S, 10'84 per cent).

2:3-Naphthathiophene-8'-(3'-chloro)-acenaphthylene-indigo.

The red-violet small needles, obtained from 3-chloro-acenaphthenequinone (0'649 g.) and 2:3-naphthoxythiophene (0'6 g.) in 70 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid by heating for 15 minutes, were purified by heating with acetic acid and crystallised from nitrobenzene in beautiful clusters of long needles. It is difficultly soluble in pyridine, xylene, moderately soluble in chloroform. It dyes cotton in red violet shades from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found : Cl, 9'24. $C_{24}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 8'91 per cent).

2 : 3-Naphthathiophene-8'-(3'-bromo)-acenaphthylene-indigo was prepared from 3-bromoty-acenaphthenequinone (0'783 g.) and 2:3-naphthoxythiophene (0'6 g.) in 80 c.c. of boiling acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The red-violet crystalline precipitate was purified and crystallised in the same way as the preceding compound. It possesses properties similar to the preceding compound. (Found : Br, 18'27. $C_{24}H_{11}O_2BrS$ requires Br, 18'05 per cent).

2 : 3-Naphthathiophene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthylene-indigo separated as deep red-violet needles from β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (1'06 g.) and 2:3-naphthoxythiophene (1 g.) in 130 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid and 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid by heating for 30 minutes. The dye is soluble in pyridine, aniline, difficultly soluble in chloroform. It dyes cotton in light violet colour. (Found : S, 7'79. $C_{25}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 8'12 per cent).